

EFFECT OF *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* INFECTION ON THE DYNAMICS OF CREATININE AND UREA CONCENTRATIONS IN THE BLOOD PLASMA OF RABBITS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to compare the dynamics of urea and creatinine, in rabbits that are infected with *Staphylococcus aureus* (experimental) and in control groups. Blood samples from each rabbit were taken as follows: at 3 months of age, coinciding with 0 hours before infection, and 6, 24, 48, 72 hours and on days 7, 14, and 21 after *S. aureus* infection. The results showed significant decreasing between groups ($P < 0.05$) of urea since 72 hours after infection to day 14. Significant increase in creatinine between groups was established on days 7 and 14 ($P < 0.01$; $P < 0.05$ respectively), and on the 6th hour after infection until the end of the experiment in the experimental group.

Key words: Urea, creatinine, plasma, New Zealand rabbit.

Introduction

When assessing rabbit diseases, it is important to know that the rabbits may mask the symptoms of the diseases or manifest some complex clinical signs. As disorders have considerable effects on blood parameters in rabbits, it is important to analyse blood and urine in rabbits as well as in other animal species (Özkan et al., 2012; Archetti et al., 2008; Betacrount et Alonso, 2011). Hence, some important findings may be achieved using haematological and biochemical parameters (Lepitzki and Woolf, 1991) and to add something novel to the profession.

The most important metabolic change in infectious diseases is the strong increase in the concentration of plasma proteins synthesized in the liver and pooled in the group of acute phase proteins (Kushner 1982, Eckersall & Conner, 1988, Pannen & Robotham, 1995, Baumann & Gauldie, 1994, Gruys et al., 1994, Raines, 1994). In this regard, we have reviewed the changes in APP (Georgieva et al., 2012, Georgieva et al., 2017, Vlaykova et al., 2011, Georgieva et al., 2012; Dyshlianova et al., 2011) and hematology (Petrov et Georgieva, 2013; Petrova et al., 2017) in experimental *St. Aureus* and *E.Coli* infection in rabbits in previous publications (Georgieva et al., 2008; Georgieva et al., 2009).

Determination of urea and creatinine in the experimental reproduction of staphylococcal infection could provide information not only for the liver and the kidney condition, but also for the intensity of metabolic changes in the body.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted with 12 male rabbits (White New Zealand), 6 of which were infected and treated in the experimental group. The experiment began when the rabbits were 3 months old and infected with *S. aureus*. They were placed in individual disinfected metal cells with grate floor and placed in a room with a temperature (20–22 °C). Their food was pelleted according to age requirements with free access to water.

The rabbits were infected intradermally with 100 μ L of the bacterial suspension of a *S. aureus* strain (density: 8×10^8 cfu / mL). The blood samples from each rabbit were taken before the euthanasia of *v. auricularis externa* as follows: 1) at 3 months of age, coinciding with 0 hours before infection, and at 6, 24, 48, 72 hours and on Days 7, 14 and 21 after *S. aureus* infection in sterile heparinized tubes. They were centrifuged immediately (1500 g, 10 min, 4 °C) and plasma was obtained. The plasma was then decanted and stored at -20 °C until the determinations were performed, except for the fibrinogen which was determined at 2 hours.

The determination of urea, creatinine, was performed by a semi-automatic biochemical analyst at the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine at the Thracian University, Stara Zagora, Bulgaria.

The statistical processing of the results obtained in the individual experiments was performed through ANOVA (Statistics for Windows, Stat Soft Ins., USA, 1993). The statistical reliability of the difference within and between groups was determined by the Posthoc procedure LSD test (Stat Soft Ins., USA, 1993). The level of statistical significance of the differences was $p < 0.05$.

Results

The level of urea in the blood of the infected rabbits significantly decreased compared to the control group over the period since 72 hours to 14 days after infection (Figure 1).

*Significance of differences between groups: * $p < 0,05$*

Figure 1: Concentration of urea in the experimental and control groups in rabbits.

Significance of differences between groups: * $p < 0,05$, ** $p < 0,01$
 Significance of differences in the experimental group comparing 0 hour (before infection)
 a $p < 0,05$ b $p < 0,01$ c $p < 0,001$

Figure 2: Concentration of creatinine in the experimental and control groups in rabbits.

During the infection, the level of creatinine fluctuated between 1.07 ± 0.04 and 1.32 ± 0.06 mg / dL, and throughout the experimental period the concentrations were significantly higher than the pre-infection period. A significant increasing compared the control group was observed at day 7 ($p < 0.01$) and 14 ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

Unlike other small animals, such as dogs and cats, where urea elevation is associated with kidney disease and an inability to radiate from the body, we observed a decrease in urea from day 4 to day 14 in rabbits infected with staphylococcus, which was associated with liver and ornithine cycle disorders, which take place in the liver. We also take in account that lower level of urea is connected with reduced synthesis of protein, because of defective liver function or the reduced intake of the protein food during infection time. Concova et al., 1999 found a significant decrease in urea level in rabbits infected with *Encephalitozoon cuniculi* and treated with albendazole only on day 60. A pronounced elevation of urea and creatinine clearance was found in rabbits infected with coccidian oocysts (Tambur et al.,1999). According to Kumar & Josh (1993), who studied a longer period (3 months after infection), creatinine and urea levels increased after experimental infection of rabbits with coccidia of the species *Staria cervi*. In our study, urea decreased from 72 hours to 14 days after infection with *S. aureus*, whereas the studies of the abov ementioned authors showed a credible urea increase of values of 19.62 ± 2.78 to 47.85 ± 5.54 mM/L during the 30th - 70th day of infection. We could assume that the differences in these results were due to the difference in the infectious agent. The same authors found a creatine increase of 81.7 ± 5.6 μ M / L

to $92.3 \pm 4.6 \mu\text{M} / \text{L}$ on the 15th day after infection. Creatinine during *S. aureus* infection in our studies was also increased from 1.06 ± 0.04 to $1.32 \pm 0.06 \text{ mg/dL}$.

Urea is an end product of the detoxification of toxic ammonia during ornithine cycle and ammonia is produced by the deamination of aminoacids during protein catabolism, and deamination of purine bases of nucleic acids. Moreover, the metabolic changes during infection time include muscle loss and negative nitrogen balance. The urea is synthesized in the liver, but excreted by the kidneys into the urine. *S.aureus* produces two types of exotoxins pyrogenic toxin superantigens (PTSAgs) and hemolysins exotoxins (Dinges et al., 2000) which are absorbed and transported by the blood into the liver and reins. PTSAgs may impair liver endotoxin clearance functions through direct cytotoxic effects on liver cells (Canonico et al., 1971) which leads to damaged hepatocells and destroyed the function of the above mentioned organs. As we observed staphylococcal abscesses concerned not only skin, but also liver. We have to mention that it is very difficult to interpret small changes in urea levels because urea levels in rabbits depend on some physiological factors like: the circadian rhythm (peak in late afternoon and early evening), quantity and quality of proteins in the diet, nutritional status, liver function, intestinal absorption, urease activity of the caecal flora, and hydration status. Moreover, the reference ranges have been determined from laboratory rabbits fed on a standardized diet and bled at the same time of the day, whereas clinicians see pet rabbits fed on a variety of foods and samples are taken at random (Hackness, 2013). According to Petkova et al., 2011 the urea concentration in New Zealand rabbits at 45-50 days of age is $5.62 \pm 0.35 \text{ mM} / \text{L}$ in males and $6.4 \pm 0.35 \text{ mM} / \text{L}$ in females, which is coincided with our results.

In our study, the initial concentration of creatinine was below 1mg/dl , which falls in the reference range for it according Hackness, 2013, who reported this range between 0.5 to $2.2 \text{ mg} / \text{dL}$ and according Ozkan et al., 2012 the reference range of creatinine are between $0,06$ и $0,14 \text{ mmol/L}$. The level of creatinine was significantly elevated since 6th hour after infection, which remained until the end of the experimental period compared to the 0 hour in the infected rabbits, and when compared to the control, a significant increase was obtained since day 14 to day 21. Orhue & Nwanze, (2005) found a significant increase in creatinine levels in rabbits infected with trypanosome on the 14th day after invasion, and explained this with impaired functional status of the kidneys, especially glomeruls. Moreover, creatinine is not influenced by non-renal factors (Hackness, 2013). In addition, rabbits have a limited ability to concentrate urine and only a few hours of lack of drinking water or diarrhea lead to increased levels of urea and creatinine, but their levels are rapidly returning to normal if dehydration ceases (Hackness, 2013).

A significant increase is indicative of a reduction in glomerular filtration rate, which may be due to infection of the glomeruli or renal pelvis. Creatinine measurement in our study was performed when there was a suspicion of disruption of glomerular urine filtration rate. Its elevated levels are an indicator of impaired kidney function (Javadi et al., 2014); (Solomon et al., 2015). Creatinine is a catabolite that is produced from the dephosphorilation of muscle creatinephospate and excreted by glomerular filtration at a constant rate. This reaction is occur when energy from the catabolism of ATP is unadequite and the organism needs an additional energy, because after infection the rabbits suffered from decreasing of appetite and the consumed food. This leads them to starvation and activation their reserves of creatinephosphate with formation of creatinine.

Therefore, we recommend that all the biochemical parameters of the herds of healthy rabbits be investigated on each farm and that the breed's reference age and gender differences should be

determined, as well as the nutrition, hydration status and response from different times of taking the blood.

Conclusion

During staphylococcal infection of rabbits the level of urea is decreased and the level of creatinine is increased which could be due to the impair function of the liver and kidneys.

References

1. Archetti, I., C. M. Cerioli, R. Brivio, G. Grilli, A. Lavazza. (2008). *Serum chemistry and hematology values in commercial rabbits: preliminary data from industrial farms in northern Italy*. In Proc.: 9th World Rabbit Congress, 10-13, June, Verona, Italy, 2008, 1147–1151. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270472124> Biochemical and physiological changes in growing rabbits fed different sources of crude fiber [accessed Jan 19 2018].
2. Betancourt-Alonso, M.A., A. Orihuela, V. Aguirre, R. Vazquez, I. Flores-Perez. (2011). *Changes in behavioural and physiological parameters associated with Taenia pisiformis infection in rabbits (Oryctolagus cuniculus) that may improve early detection of sick rabbits*. World Rabbit Sciences, 2011, 19, 21-30. Biotechnology in Animal Husbandry, 2011, 27, 3, 1367–1378.
3. Canonico, P. G., M. J. Van Zweiten. (1971). *Swelling of mitochondria from rabbit liver induced by staphylococcal enterotoxin*. British Journal Infect. Dis., 1971, 124, 372–378.
4. Concova, E., E. Cellarova, J. Neuschl, M. Halanova. (1999). *The dynamics of creatinine and urea concentrations in the blood serum of rabbits infected by Encephalitozoon.cuniculi microsporidium and treated with albendazole*. 1999. Acta Veterinaria ISSN:0567–8315.
5. Dinges, M. M., P. M. Orwin, & P. M. Schlievert. (2000). *Exotoxins of Staphylococcus aureus*. Clinical microbiology reviews, 2000,13, 1, 16–34.DOI: 10.4995/wrs.2011.801
6. Dyshlianova, E., T. M. Georgieva, V. Petrov, D. Zapryanova, P. Marutsov, I. Dinev, I. Nikiforov, I. Penchev Georgiev. (2011). *Blood haptoglobin response in rabbits with experimentally induced S. aureus infection*. Revue Médecine Vétérinaire, 2011, 162, 11, 514–518.
7. Eckersall, P. D. & J. G. Conner. (1990). *Plasma haptoglobin in cattle (Bos Taurus) exists as in with albumin polymers*. Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, 1990, 96B, 309–314.
8. Georgieva, T. M., V. Petrov, Iv. P. Georgiev, N. Nikolova, M. Lyutskanov, N. Bozakova. (2017). *Study on the total proteins and main protein fractions in rabbits experimentally infected with staphylococcus aureus*. Trakia Journal of Sciences, 2017, 1, 42-49, Copyright © 2017 Trakia University.
9. Georgieva, T. M., V. Petrov, I. P. Georgiev, D. Zapryanova, P. Marutsov, N. Rusenova, P. Parvanov. (2016). *Effect of staphylococcus aureus infection on plasma creatine kinase activity in rabbits*. Trakia Journal of Sciences, 2016, 14, 1, 52–60.
10. Georgieva, T. M., I. P. Georgiev, Y. Iliev, V. S. Petrov, A. Vachkov, I. N. Kanelov, S. I. Tanev, D. Zapryanova, A. I. Pavlov and D. Eckersall. (2008). *Blood serum concentrations of total proteins and main protein fractions in weaning rabbits experimentally infected with E. coli*. Revue de Médecine Vétérinaire, 2008, 159, 8–9, 431–436.
11. Georgieva, T. M., S. Denev, V. Petrov, I. Dinev, Y. Saco, R. Pato, A. Bassols, I. Nikiforov. (2012). *Effects of experimentally induced Staphylococcus aureus infection on blood protein fractions in obese rabbits*. Revue de Médecine Vétérinaire, 2012, 163, 6, 276–280.
12. Georgieva, T. M., T. Vlaykova, E. Dishlianova, Vl. Petrov and I. Penchev Georgiev. (2012). *The behaviour of ceruloplasmin as an acute phase protein in obese and infected rabbits*. Farm Animal Proteomics. Proceedings of the 3rd Managing Committee Meeting and 2nd Meeting of Working Groups 1, 2 and 3 of COST Action FA1002, Vilamoura, Portugal, 67–70 (Eds.) Rodrigues P., D. Eckersall and Andre de Almeida, Wageningen Academic Publishers, The Netherlands, 2012 ISBN:978-90-8686-195-8.
13. Georgieva, T. M., I. P. Georgiev, V. S. Petrov, A. Vachkov, S. I. Tanev, A. I. Pavlov and D. Eckersall. (2009). *Variations of acute phase proteins in weaning rabbits experimentally infected with E. coli*. Revue de Médecine Vétérinaire, 2009, 160, 3, 133–139.
14. Georgieva, T. M., V. Petrov, I. P. Georgiev, D. Zapryanova, L. Lazarov, Ts. Christov, Y. P. Petrova, P. Iliev, F. Cecilliani. (2017). *Changes in blood lipid profile in rabbits after experimental*

- infection with Staphylococcus aureus*. Bulgarian Journal of Veterinary Medicine, 2017, 20, Suppl. 1, 345–351.
15. Harkness, J., E. Patricia, V. Turner, Susan Vande Woude Colette, L. Wheler Harkness and Wagner's. *Biology and Medicine of Rabbits and Rodents*. John Wiley & Sons., 120 ISSN 1450-9156
 16. Javadi, S., S. Asri-Rezaei, M. Allahverdizadeh. (2014). *Interrelationship of beta-2 microglobulin, blood urea nitrogen and creatinine in streptozotocin-induced diabetes mellitus in rabbits*. Veterinary Research Forum, 2014, 5, 1, 7–11.
 17. Jenkins, J. R. (2008). *Rabbit diagnostic testing*. Journal of Exotic Pet Medicine, 2008, 17, 4–15
 18. Kumar, M. and H.C. Josh. (1993). *Blood chemical alterations in experimental Setaria cervi infection in rabbits*. Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Science, 1993, 6, 4, 491–495.
 19. Lepitzki, D. A., A. Woolf. (1991). *Hematology and serum chemistry of cottontail rabbits of southern Illinois*. Journal of Wildlife Diseases, 1991, 27, 643–649.
 20. Orhue, N. E. J., E. A. Nwanze. (2005). *Increases in plasma urea and creatinine in experimental Trypanosoma brucei infection is influenced by Scoparia Dulcis*. Ann.Biomed.Sci., 2005, 4, 1, 35–41.
 21. Ozkan, C., A. Kaya, Y. Akgul. (2012). *Normal values of haematological and some biochemical parameters in serum and urine of New Zealand White rabbits*. World Rabbit Science, 2012, 20, 253–259.
 22. Petkova, M., S. Grigorova, D. Abadjieva. (2011). *Biochemical and physiological changes in growing rabbits fed different sources of crude fiber*. Biotechnology in Animal Husbandry 2011, 27, 3, 1367–1378. ISSN 1450-9156, Publisher: Institute for Animal Husbandry, Belgrade-Zemun.
 23. Petrova, Y., T. Georgieva, I. Georgiev, V. Petrov, I. Kalkanov, M. Karadaev, S. Stoev, F. Ceciliani. (2017). *Changes in parameters of red blood count in New Zealand White Rabbits after experimentally induced P. multocida infection*. 19th International Veterinary Medicine Students Scientific Research Congress, Istanbul, 2017, May 02-04, 294.
 24. Solomon, I. P.1., S. A. Oyebadejo, E. M. Ukpo and O. S. Joseph. (2015). *Changes in serum electrolyte, creatinine and urea of fresh Citrus limon juice administered to growing rabbits (Oryctolagus cuniculus)*. International Journal of Agricultural Science Research, August 2015, 4, 8, 180–183.
 25. Tambur, Z., Z. Kulisic, Z. Malicevic, M. Mihailovic. *Blood glucose, plasma osmolarity and urea and creatinine clearance in rabbits artificially infeted with intestinal coccidian*. Concentration Acta Veterinaria, 49, 2, 171–176. UDC 636.085.
 26. Vlaykova, T., E. Dishlyanova, V. Petrov, P. Marutsov, I. Penchev. T. Mircheva. (2011). *Changes of PON1 activity, total thiols and ferrous reducing ability of plasma during acute inflammation of rabbits with St. aureus*. COST-Farm Animal Proteomics Spring Meeting, 2011. Abstracts-Poster Presentation WG1, Abstract book (eds.)
 27. Almeida A., M. McLaughlin and D. Eckersall. *Pfizer – Animal Health*. 2011, 61.
 28. Петров, В., Т. М. Георгиева. (2013). *Хематологични изследвания при затлъстели и незатлъстели зайци с експериментална Staphylococcus aureus инфекция*. Bulgarian Journal of Veterinary Medicine, 2013, 16, Suppl. 1, 121–133.